

Review

What is important for consumers' energy-related decisions? A cross-sectoral systematic review and meta-analysis for the Nordic countries

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ABSTRACT

The energy transition is shaped by the decisions of individuals. These decisions, in turn, are influenced by a diverse set of factors that have been the object of various studies reported in the literature. Most of these studies have, however, focused on a single decision or a sector. Here, we conduct for the Nordic countries a systematic literature review and a meta-analysis of factors affecting four important consumers' energy-related decisions, namely (1) the choice between an electric or a conventional vehicle, (2) mode choice for personal transport, (3) choice of heating system, and (4) deployment of energy-saving measures at home. We aim to identify the implications that certain factors may have for many of such decisions, potentially encouraging some while discouraging others. Our analysis shows that a group of factors, such as attitude, comfort, costs, living in a detached house, emission implications of the choice, perceived behavioral control, environmental friendliness of the technology, and subjective norm, affect multiple decisions uniformly, in terms of the direction of effect the factor has on environmentally benign decisions. There are, however, also factors for which trade-offs exist, for example, while better public transport infrastructure encourages the use of public transport use, it discourages walking and cycling. We also show differences in outcomes between revealed and stated preferences surveys. Our analysis shows that for electric vehicle adoption, the statistical significance of factors typically increases when excluding the stated preferences surveys. Finally, our findings can aid policymakers in crafting more effective interventions to meet climate targets.

1. Introduction

Individuals, through their choices, affect the direction the energy transition will take. As these choices are typically driven by factors going beyond economic and technical ones, scientific discussions have correspondingly gone beyond these disciplines to identify the drivers and barriers of energy-related decisions [1]. These efforts have identified various factors influencing the decision-making process, including financial, contextual, psychological, social, and technical ones [2].

Residential and transport sectors are responsible for more than half of global energy-related carbon dioxide emissions [3,4] and four energy-related decisions in these sectors have been widely identified as particularly important for the energy transition: (1) Whether to purchase an electric or conventional vehicle, (2) mode choice for personal transport, (3) choice of heating system at home, and (4) implementation of energy-saving measures at home (ref. [5], for example, highlights all four decisions). Various review studies [6–16] have investigated the large body of literature studying the factors influencing these decisions.

For example, the acceptance [6] and adoption [10,11,14,15] of electric vehicles (EVs), car and non-car use [13], low-carbon mode choice [12], or mode choice in general [9], and energy-saving measures [7,8,16] have been reviewed. These review studies have, however, been sectoral, typically focusing on a specific, single energy-related decision, and thus have not captured possible wider implications the factors may have across multiple energy-related choices, potentially encouraging some while discouraging others. The review studies have also generally overlooked cultural variety [17] in the evidence, aggregating results from different cultural and geographical areas, sometimes even globally [6], which can lead to conclusions clouded by the cultural variety of the respondents. Also, the previous reviews on this topic have not considered the possible attitude-action gap [18], with much of the evidence reflecting outcomes of stated preferences surveys, rather than revealed preferences ones, and not differentiating the evidence on this criterion. The difference between these two types of surveys stems from the data collection process where the revealed preferences surveys focus on observing actual behaviors or choices that individuals make in real-

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world situations, but the stated preferences ones try to ask people directly about their preferences in hypothetical situations.

The objective of this study is to fill this gap and analyze the role that specific factors play in the different decisions. More specifically, we aim to answer the following research questions:

- Are there factors that are consistently significant for multiple decisions? What are these factors?
- Is their impact always supportive of environmentally friendly choices, or does this depend on the choices being investigated?
- How consistent is the evidence across the studies for each factor and decision, in terms of statistical significance and direction of the influence?
- For which factors is there also empirical evidence (i.e. revealed preferences studies) to be found, and which rely purely on stated preference studies? Do the results change, if only revealed preference studies are considered?

To answer our research questions, we carry out an interdisciplinary meta-analysis to improve the accuracy of conclusions and to better understand the contrasting findings from individual studies. Meta-analyses play a crucial role in gathering information within a particular research area, offering a valuable tool for summarizing research outcomes [19]. The necessity of such an analysis in our case lies within the complex nature of decision-making, affected by numerous known and sometimes unknown factors, varying from study to study. For example, each questionnaire is likely to have slightly different questions, collected at different points in time and thus reflecting slightly different decision environments. Thus, to assess what can be concluded from the heterogeneous evidence base from the various studies, it is important to gather evidence to draw conclusions from the available studies. As cultural variation across countries affects e.g. purchase behavior [20], we limit the abovementioned context variation by focusing our review on a set of culturally similar countries, the Nordic countries,¹ to improve the robustness of our results. These countries are also further along in some areas of the energy transition, e.g. for electric mobility [21] and heat pumps [22], and thus studies from these countries are more likely to provide also empirical evidence about the diffusion of low-emission technologies. Nevertheless, we hope the results of this analysis can offer insights into the factors influencing energy-related decisions also for other countries, e.g. by providing a reference point against which the other country can be compared.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section 2 presents the methodology of this review and meta-analysis. Section 3 provides the results and discusses the findings of this work. Finally, section 4 concludes the paper and suggests avenues for future research works.

2. Methodology

In this section, the literature review stages are discussed. First, the relevance and inclusion criteria for the review are thoroughly explained and the number of remaining articles after each stage is shown. Then, the extraction of data, categorization of factors, classification of factor categories, and at the end the super categorization of factor categories are presented to describe the various steps that have been taken to analyze the data.

2.1. The literature review process

The systematic review involves multiple stages based on the PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses) protocol (Fig. 1), which is a recognized framework used in health, medical, and social sciences to conduct systematic reviews and meta-

analyses [23]. In the first stage, a search string incorporating the characteristics of the targeted literature has iteratively been developed and refined for each decision by comparing the emerging search results with the set of literature known to be relevant. The search strings consist of three elements, each focusing on a specific aspect of the studies, namely the decision, factor, and case study (see Supplementary Data). Using the search strings on the ninth of August 2022, holding the assumption that peer-reviewed studies are more dependable, a total of 261 English peer-reviewed articles were identified through the Web of Science academic database. The search strings were again used in Web of Science and Scopus databases on the third of July 2023 in order to find the newly published papers and expand the search domain. Then, the duplicates were removed. In the second stage of review, the title and abstract of the studies were assessed while considering the relevance criteria (see Table 1) to ensure the article is about the decisions that individuals or households make and also presents factors affecting those decisions. The final review stage was done based on full-text screening. The inclusion criteria by which the articles have been selected check whether the case study of the articles are Nordic countries, whether the studies are based on a survey, whether the articles present the direction of influence of the factors, and whether the statistical significance level of each factor is available. The fifth inclusion criterion was considered since in the presence of a reference mode/heating system, the other choices are compared to the reference mode, and the factors assessed in the study are examined for their effects on the choice of an alternative mode/heating system over the reference one. Therefore, as the reference modes differ among various studies, the results of such analyses could not be effectively used in our meta-analysis. Following the aforementioned rigorous process, 53 studies were identified as meeting the pre-determined criteria [24–76]. See the Supplementary Data for the list of references existing in each stage of the review. We did not limit the search to any specific period, and the studies analyzed were published between 2006 and 2022.

2.2. Data extraction

The following information has been carefully collected from the article after reading them (see Supplementary Data): methods used, year of publication, implementation year of the survey (if available), case studies, type of survey (revealed or stated preferences), number of respondents, the response rate of the survey, technologies and measures, the factors that are not statistically significant, and the sign of the coefficient of the statistically significant factors. A statistical significance level of 0.05 and lower was considered significant. In the process of data extraction, if a source used two different methods with a data set, both were considered separately as individual pieces of evidence.

As we aimed to gain a broad insight into the factors for each of the four decisions, and more essentially, find the influential factors that cut across these decisions, every piece of evidence found in the literature that pertains to one of the four decisions is deemed equally important, regardless of the specific choice or population it addresses. For instance, some studies have assessed different populations (e.g. battery electric vehicle users and internal combustion engine users or couples and single-person households) for the EV adoption decision, different trips in the case of modal choice decision (e.g. trips in summer and winter or with different purposes such as work, routine, leisure, shopping, commuting, etc.), and different energy-saving measures (e.g. retrofit measures, energy-saving behaviors, etc.). We included such studies in our body of evidence, just as we did those that did not target specific populations or more narrowly defined decision categories.

While extracting the data from the papers, various car and heating technologies and also several transport modes emerge throughout the literature. For EV adoption, the technologies that appear in the literature are EVs in general, Battery Electric Vehicles (BEV), and Plug-in Hybrid Electric Vehicles (PHEV). For this review, we considered all three technologies as electric vehicles but acknowledge that influencing

¹ The Nordic countries are: Denmark, Finland, Iceland, Norway, and Sweden.

Fig. 1. Stages and flow of the literature review.

Table 1
Relevance and inclusion criteria for the systematic literature review.

Criterion type	Criterion
Relevance criteria	1. The study should be about the decisions of individuals or households. 2. The study should present factors that influence the decisions.
Inclusion criteria	1. The case study should be Nordic countries. 2. The study should be based on a survey. 3. The factors should be presented with their direction of influence. 4. The statistical significance level for each factor should be available. 5. An additional criterion for the mode choice and heating system adoption is that there should not be a reference mode or technology to which the transport mode or heating system is compared.

factors may differ across the technologies. For mode choice, the evaluated modes in the papers are car, public and active transport in general, internal combustion engine cars in particular, bus, bicycle, and walking. We reflect on the three primary modes of transport: cars, public transport, and active transport, incorporating findings from the other specific transport modes within these categories. For heating system adoption,

different names have been used to describe the technologies in the literature. The emerged technologies from the reviewed studies are the following: wood pellets, solid wood-fired, district heating, ground heat, heating by electricity, electric storage heating, exhaust air heat pump, oil heater, heat pump, wood pellet stove, and electric heating. Using the information in the papers, we combined these technologies into five categories of technology which are electric heating (including heating by electricity, electric storage heating, and electric heating), heat pump (including ground heat, exhaust air heat pump, and heat pump), solid heater (including wood pellets, solid wood-fired, wood pellet stove), oil heater, and district heating. Furthermore, two of the papers have discussed the decision to buy a new heating system regardless of the technology type. We evaluated this item along with the others as well.

The reason we distinguished between different transport modes and heating system technologies is that the evidence for consumer preferences toward two completely different modes/technologies cannot be aggregated due to their inherent differences, which are arguably larger than differences between various EV types, for example.

2.3. Categorization of factors

Having the list of factors emerging from the literature for each decision and observing the similarities between a wide range of factors that have common themes, we categorized the factors affecting each decision

to obtain a holistic view of what groups of factors influence the decisions. We categorized some factors into a single category when they are conceptually similar, proxy of a variable, or just worded differently across the studies. For instance, “charging time” and “charging speed” have a similar concept but are worded differently in two different studies, or for example, “price” and “operation cost” both reflect the costs related to car use. The name of a category was chosen in such a way that it can represent the similar concept of the underlying factors. Considering the mentioned criteria, the extracted factors for each decision were categorized (see Supplementary Data). Some factors did not fit into any category and thus formed their own.

The evidence for a category is the aggregation of the evidence of each factor within the category. Some factors are defined in such a way that the sign of their coefficient should be reversed to match the other factors in their category. For instance, the category of “charging time” includes two factors: “charging time” and “charging speed”. As the charging speed increases, the charging time decreases, thus, the sign of the coefficient of the charging speed was reversed. The factors that the sign of their coefficient was reversed are tagged with a star in Supplementary Data.

We acknowledge the subjectiveness of this process. Tighter scrutiny in the categorization would lead to more factor categories, and to more factor categories constituting just one factor. This would, on average, reduce the amount of evidence for factor categories, making it more difficult to draw conclusions about them. On the other hand, a more relaxed categorization could affect the consistency of the evidence, i.e. the aggregation process itself may show up as inconsistency in the evidence base for a factor category. The factors considered in this study for each factor category are presented in Supplementary Data.

2.4. Classification of factor categories

We used the factor categories to analyze the evidence using a classification based on four indexes. The first index is the amount of evidence (i.e. number of studies), assisting us to identify whether the evidence is enough to decide on factor effectiveness. The second index is “statistical insignificance” which is equal to the number of evidence indicating the factor category is non-significant divided by the total number of evidence. This index shows to what degree a factor category has been found non-significant in the surveys. It should be noted that statistical significance is a different term and has its own definition relating to the significance of a variable in a study. Our “statistical insignificance” index, however, shows summary information about the significance of a factor category among the reviewed body of literature. The third index is “directional consistency” which is an index to display the consistency in the direction of influence of a factor category in the body of literature. Using the number of evidence indicating a positive effect (P) and the number of evidence indicating a negative effect (N), eq. (1) shows how this index is calculated. For example, the index will be equal to 1, 0.9, 0.8, ..., 0.2, and 0.1 if 100 %, 95 %, 90 %, ..., 60 %, and 55 % of the evidence that shows a direction of influence agrees on a specific direction respectively. The index will be equal to zero for the factor categories that the number of evidence showing positive effect is equal to the number of evidence showing negative effect. Therefore, as the index increases, the evidence for a factor category is more directionally consistent. The fourth index is whether there is at least one piece of evidence that is based on a revealed preferences survey. This index informs us if the evidence contains information obtained from empirical data or is only based on the stated preferences of individuals.

$$\text{Directional Consistency} = \frac{|P - N|}{P + N} \quad (1)$$

Based on the four described indexes, we then divided the factor categories into six classes as follows:

Class 1 Influential with also empirical evidence: All evidence shows the factor categories as statistically significant, with a consistent direction of

influence throughout the surveys, of which at least one is a revealed preferences survey.

Class 2 Influential without empirical evidence: As class 1, but all surveys reflect stated preferences.

Class 3 Inconclusive: More than half, but not all, evidence shows the factor categories as statistically significant, and/or not all evidence agrees on the direction of the influence (see Supplementary Note 1 for the exception).

Class 4 Non-influential: Half or less of the evidence shows the factor categories as statistically significant.

Class 5 Influential, but lack of evidence: Statistically significant, but only one study reports on the factor category.

Class 6 Non-influential, but lack of evidence: Not statistically significant, but only one study reports on the factor category.

See Supplementary Note 1 for the exact conditions the factor categories should satisfy to be included in each class and further discussion on the classification process to illustrate why such rules have been considered for the classification.

2.5. Super categorization of factor categories

Following the categorization and classification processes, the factor categories in the first four classes, which are the factor categories that do not lack evidence, were further categorized into a higher level of categories called super categories (see Fig. 2 and Supplementary Data). The super categorization is conducted across all the energy-related decisions to assess the factor categories that are important for various choices. The aim is to broaden the evidence base, as we use the super categories to analyze the impact of factors on multiple different decisions simultaneously. Similarly to the initial categorization, the factor categories that appear for different decisions and are conceptually close, proxy of a variable, or just worded differently, have been considered within a super category which is named to represent the concept of the underlying factor categories. In addition, as some factor categories show different aspects of a single categorical variable, we created some super categories that represent such categorical variables. For example, “being in Denmark”, “being in Sweden”, and “being in Norway” are considered within a super category of “region and area”, or for instance, because different existing heating technologies are found to be important for choices of heating system, we put all the existing technologies in a single super category called “existing technology”. There are factor categories that did not fall into any super category and formed their own. The factor categories within each super category are presented in Supplementary Data.

The review and meta-analysis process is developed by the authors to ensure the replicability of the analysis using transparently defined criteria and indexes. However, there are steps in the categorization and super categorization processes that are subjective in nature. It should also be noted that the screening, data extraction, factor categorization, and super categorization were done by one of the authors, which enabled methodological consistency, however, the other author validated the process through several reviews and examinations.

3. Results and discussion

In this section, the results of the systematic literature review are presented. In sub-section 3.1, we lay out the extracted data from the literature and discuss the outcomes of the classification of factor categories to assess how consistent the evidence is across the studies for each factor category both in terms of statistical significance and direction of influence. Then, in sub-section 3.2, we assess the impact of survey type on the effects of several factor categories on the decisions, and how they differ if the survey is based on revealed versus stated preferences of respondents. Finally, in sub-section 3.3, super categories are used to examine their influence on various decisions to find factors that are consistently significant for multiple decisions and understand whether

Fig. 2. Categorization, classification, and super categorization of the factors.

Fig. 3. The evidence base of the review. The evidence is disaggregated in terms of decision (inner ring), geographical scope (middle ring), and survey type (outer ring). RP and SP represent revealed and stated preferences survey respectively. EVA, MC, HSA, and ESM are EV adoption, mode choice, heating system adoption, and energy-saving measures respectively.

their impact is always supportive of environmentally friendly choices or not.

3.1. Laying out the factors

The data extracted from the literature shows how numerous factors have been examined for their possible effect on electric vehicle adoption (EVA), mode choice (MC), heating system adoption (HSA), and energy-saving measures (ESM). We found 158, 172, 49, and 68 factors investigated for EVA, MC, HSA, and ESM respectively, followed by the extraction of 1492 data points on the significance and direction of the effect of factors from the body of evidence: 337, 521, 239, and 395 data points for EVA, MC, HSA, and ESM respectively. The evidence base is mainly focused on Sweden ($N = 53$), Norway ($N = 38$), and Denmark ($N = 14$) and to a less extent on Finland ($N = 7$) and Iceland ($N = 2$) (Fig. 3). The distribution of evidence between the decisions indicates the lack of surveys on heating system adoption. Furthermore, although the body of evidence based on empirical data is strong (65 out of 114 pieces of evidence), there is only one revealed preferences study on heating system adoption, highlighting a relative research gap. This also hinders us from effectively assessing the differences between the results of stated and revealed preferences surveys on this decision.

This categorization process yields 102, 113, 42, and 57 factor categories for EVA, MC, HSA, and ESM respectively. Subsequently, the classification to the six factor category classes has been done, as described in the methodology section. The influential factor categories (Class 1 and Class 2 as described in Section 2) are shown in Table 2, shown for the four different decision categories, with mode and heating system choice further split based on modes and technologies, respectively.

A considerable number of the factor categories have not been considered in many studies (see Supplementary Fig. 1), and this applies also to the factor categories that are influential. Further investigations on the factors with a lower number of evidence would increase confidence in the interpretation of outcomes and could also yield different results. There are, however, some factor categories in Class 1 and Class 2 with more evidence supporting the conclusion about them. The factor categories that have “high” or “very high” number of evidence (>6 pieces of evidence) – and include also empirical evidence – are functional barriers for EV adoption, and having access to car and public transport infrastructure (e.g. bus, metro, and train stations), affecting the choice of public and active transport respectively (see Supplementary Data for the factors considered in each factor category). The evidence base is also strong for the cost of heating system adoption, but without any empirical data. Although many factor categories are supported by the empirical data, there are also a few that have not been investigated by the revealed preferences surveys.

Table 1 excludes factor categories that were considered inconclusive (Class 3). Considering the rather strict criteria we have established for our influential factor categories, with all the evidence having to be fully supportive of the conclusions about significance and direction, and taking into account the effect our aggregation of factors into factor categories may introduce to these metrics, we analyze the factor categories in this class further. Some of these factor categories may, in reality, be influential, but the processes of data extraction (which might have been affected by the potential Table 2 fallacy in the underlying studies [77]) and categorization have affected the outcome, consumer behavior and perception of technologies may have changed over the time range covered by the studies, attitude-action gap may affect the classification, and biases such as publication bias [78] might impact the statistical significance of factor categories (see also Supplementary Note 2 and Supplementary Table 2). Due to this, we want to further investigate this class and its evidence base.

In Fig. 4, we depict metrics for the inconclusive factor categories, for “directional consistency” and “statistical insignificance”. The closer the directional consistency and statistical insignificance indexes are to one

and zero respectively, the closer we are to the factor categories being classed as influential. On the other hand, the closer the statistical insignificance index is to 0.5, the more likely it is to be considered non-influential. Fig. 4 depicts the inconclusive factor categories for EV adoption, with information also about the size of the evidence base, presence of empirical data and direction of the influence. Similar figures for the inconclusive factor categories of the other decisions are available in Supplementary Data.

The results show that directional consistency is not the main reason that prevents most of these factor categories from being considered influential, but the statistical significance is. The direction of effect for many factor categories has been consistent in the literature, however, there is a considerable amount of evidence suggesting statistical non-significance for the inconclusive factor categories (see Supplementary Fig. 2). For instance, in Fig. 4, the directional consistency for the majority of factor categories is equal or close to one, meaning that most of the evidence base is in favor of single direction of effect. However, except for charging infrastructure, education, incentives, personal norm, car costs, and environmental behavior factor categories, the statistical significance of none of them has been approved by >70 % of the evidence base. Also, the figure shows that the factor categories demonstrating higher significance and consistency have usually been investigated by many studies, unlike the others with a weaker evidence base. This suggests that further studies on the latter could move these factor categories toward the left – or drop them to Class 4 (Non-Influential).

As for the non-influential factor categories (Class 4), most of them have at least one piece of evidence suggesting their statistical significance, but with the majority of evidence showing the opposite. Several factor categories have five or more pieces of evidence, suggesting that they have broadly been considered as potentially significant for driving decisions, but in the end, mostly turned out not to do so. For example, environmental concern and income for EV adoption and energy-saving measures both. All such factor categories can be found in the Supplementary Data.

There are also some factor categories in the non-influential class that are never found to be statistically significant. Examples include, for instance, gender for using public transport and house size for energy-saving measures, with >4 pieces of evidence supporting them. Supplementary Table 1 shows all non-influential factor categories that are statistically non-significant throughout the data.

Finally, the fifth and sixth classes encompass the factor categories that only have one piece of evidence supporting or rejecting their significance, which we consider in our classification as inadequate. These classes can, in our categorization, be considered as experiments conducted in only few studies, but which require repetition to increase the confidence in the findings. The full list of factor categories for these classes is available in Supplementary Data.

3.2. Revealed versus stated preferences

The difference between what people say and what they actually do [14] may explain some of the contradictions observed for the inconclusive and non-influential factor categories throughout the literature. To investigate this hypothesis, we assessed the difference between directional consistency and statistical insignificance derived from (1) only empirical evidence and (2) all evidence for the inconclusive and non-influential factor categories (Class 3 and 4 above) that have at least two pieces of revealed preferences evidence and one piece of stated preferences evidence (Fig. 5).

As shown, using the evidence from the revealed preferences studies generally improves directional consistency. This is, however, not the case for all factor categories, meaning that empirical observations sometimes provide more contradictory evidence about the direction of the effect than the combined data does. The general direction of the evidence from empirical and all evidence remains the same, except for

Table 2

Influential factor categories (Class 1 and Class 2, see Section 2.4). The multiplicity of evidence (i.e. unweighted number of studies) is shown by four levels based on the number of evidence; Low (2–3), Medium (4–6), High (7–9), and Very high (10–12).

Decision/Choice	Factor category	Direction of effect	Empirical evidence	Multiplicity of evidence
Electric vehicle adoption	Access to second home	+	✓	Low
	Business or economics college degree-male (interaction factor)	+	✓	Low
	Detached house	+	✓	Low
	Immigrant parents	+	✓	Low
	Male government employee (interaction factor)	+	✓	Low
	Male municipality employee (interaction factor)	+	✓	Low
	Region of residence	+/- [†]	✓	Low
	Technical college degree-male (interaction factor)	+	✓	Low
	Travel to work 15-100 km	+	✓	Low
	Travel to work 5-15 km	+	✓	Low
	Wealth	+	✓	Low
	Female government employee (interaction factor)	-	✓	Low
	Female municipality employee (interaction factor)	-	✓	Low
	Male immigrant from high income country (interaction factor)	-	✓	Low
	Travel to work >100 km	-	✓	Low
	Attitude	+	✗	Medium
	Boot size (trunk space)	+	✗	Low
	Being in Sweden	+	✗	Low
	Environmental norm	+	✗	Medium
	Personal Innovativeness	+	✗	Low
Status and excitement	+	✗	Medium	
Subjective norm	+	✗	Low	
Charging time	-	✗	Low	
CO ₂ emission	-	✗	Low	
Functional Barriers	-	✗	Very high	
Mode choice-Car	Comfort	+	✓	Medium
	Habit	+	✓	Medium
	Number of children 7-12 years old	+	✓	Medium
	Number of legs in trip chain	+	✓	Medium
	Perceived behavioral control	+	✓	Medium
	Subjective norm	+	✓	Low
	Winter	+	✓	Medium
	Minimum density at destination	-	✓	Medium
Age squared	-	✓	Medium	
Mode choice-Public transport	Attitude	+	✓	Low
	Public transport infrastructure	+	✓	Low
	Car access	-	✓	High
	Travel time	-	✓	Low
Mode choice-Active transport	Affective motives	+	✓	Low
	Attitude	+	✓	Low
	Mix in the main uses of buildings-home	-	✓	Low
	Mix in the main uses of buildings-school	-	✓	Low
	Number of housing units per hectare-home	-	✓	Low
	Number of housing units per hectare-school	-	✓	Low
	Number of residents per sq km-home	-	✓	Low
	Number of residents per sq km-school	-	✓	Low
	Proportion of land covered by public buildings-home	-	✓	Low
	Proportion of parks and recreation areas-home	-	✓	Low
	Proportion of parks and recreation areas-school	-	✓	Low
	Public transport infrastructure	-	✓	High
Ratio of signalized intersections to total number of street intersections-school	-	✓	Low	

	Ratio of 4-way intersections to total number of street intersections-school	-	✓	Low
	Summed floor space in all the buildings divided by buffer area-home	-	✓	Low
	Summed floor space in all the buildings divided by buffer area-school	-	✓	Low
	Total road lengths divided by the drawn school journey length-school	-	✓	Low
Buying a new heating system	Buyer of environmentally friendly products	+	✓	Low
	Age of residence	+	✓	Low
	Apartment	-	✓	Low
	Level of satisfaction with current heating system	-	✗	Low
Electric heating	Comfort of use	+	✗	Low
	Electricity is existing technology	+	✗	Low
	Environmental friendliness	+	✗	Low
	Outside air heat pump is available	+	✗	Low
Heat pump	Comfort of use	+	✗	Medium
	Environmental friendliness	+	✗	Medium
	Ground heat is existing technology	+	✗	Low
	Solar panel/solar water heater is available	+	✗	Medium
	Cost	-	✗	Very high
	Repetition decision strategy	-	✗	Low
	Emissions	-	✗	Low
	Indoor air quality	-	✗	Low
Solid heater	Comfort of use	+	✗	Medium
	Environmental friendliness	+	✗	Medium
	Living in a sparsely populated area	+	✗	Low
	Solid wood fired is existing technology	+	✗	Low
Oil heater	Cost	-	✗	Medium
District heating	Comfort of use	+	✗	Low
	Environmental friendliness	+	✗	Low
	House is in district heating area	+	✗	Low
	Cost	-	✗	High
Energy-saving measures	Attitude	+	✓	Medium
	Being in Denmark	+	✓	Low
	Detached housing	+	✓	Medium
	Number of household members less than 12 years old	+	✓	Low
	General environmental attitude	+	✗	Low
	Personal norm	+	✗	Medium
	Residence in urban area	-	✗	Low

‡Depending on the region of residence it can either have a positive or negative effect.

the factor category “number of cars in household”, which affects EV adoption positively based on empirical data and negatively with all evidence combined.

Use of empirical evidence alone generally improves the statistical insignificance indicator (lowering it) for factor categories, especially for the choice of EV adoption. Three factor categories of EV adoption, namely incentives, personal norm, and children in household, are found to be influential (Class 1) after excluding the evidence from the stated preferences studies. This is also the case for perceived behavioral control for choice of public transport. At least for these factors, the revealed preferences studies have thus been able to identify the influence of factors more effectively. Naturally, the empirical evidence base for such factor categories is now even lower than the previously combined body of evidence.

In terms of our key interest, i.e. factor categories affecting multiple decisions, age, gender, and income are more statistically significant for EV adoption and energy-saving measures, when only revealed preferences studies are considered. However, this is not the case for the other factor categories (see Supplementary Data).

3.3. Common factors across the decisions

Our initial factor categorization is decision-specific, so that we can capture also factors that are relevant only for certain decisions. In order

to assess the factor categories that may be important for various decision contexts, we have further aggregated them into “super categories” (see Supplementary Data) as described in Section 2. Doing this allows us to identify broader super categories that affect decisions for more than one choice (Fig. 6). Specific super categories are represented in Fig. 6 in both, panel a and panel b. This means that while the super category is influential (Class 1 and Class 2) for some decisions (shown in panel a), it isn't that (Class 3 and Class 4) for others (those in panel b). In panel b the direction of the effect is defined only from the majority of pieces of evidence that are statistically significant.

There are super categories of factors in panel a of Fig. 6 affecting multiple choices uniformly in terms of direction of influence and statistical significance, namely attitude, comfort (e.g. ease of taking action and/or use of the technology), costs, living in a detached house, emissions following the choice made, perceived behavioral control, environmental friendliness of the technology, and subjective norm. Perceived behavioral control and subjective norm were found to be influential in the transport sector decisions, affecting EV adoption and mode choice for car use. Furthermore, while costs and environmental friendliness are found to be important in the residential sector for the choice of various heating systems, attitude, comfort, residing in a detached house and tendency to adopt a technology with lower emissions encourage the environmentally benign choices cross-sectorally. As before, the number of studies is, however, fairly low for some of these,

Fig. 4. Inconclusive factor categories for EV adoption. The diameter of the circle illustrates the size of the evidence base, letters p and n are for positive and negative effects in the majority of the statistically significant evidence base for the factor category (in turn shown by the number after the comma). Red text means there is no empirical evidence for the factor category, and black that there is at least revealed preference study for the factor category. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 5. Comparison of results between empirical and full evidence bases for the inconclusive and non-influential factor categories. The axes show the difference between revealed preferences evidence (+) and combined evidence (-). For three factor categories that have no statistically significant evidence based on the empirical data, namely social effects for EV adoption, subjective norm for mode choice-public transport, and age for energy-saving measures, only the change in the statistical insignificance is shown.

Fig. 6. Influence of factor super categories across the choices (numbered 1–11). Panel (a): Choices in which super categories are influential. Green markers do not have any empirical evidence supporting them, blue ones have at least one piece of empirical evidence. Panel (b): Choices in which super categories are inconclusive (red) or non-influential (black). Both panels: Circle and square represent positive and negative effects, respectively (majority for panel b). Triangle is used for the super categories for which the direction of influence is by nature categorical (region, occupation, and existing technology). Diamonds in panel b indicate a directional consistency index of zero, or that all evidence suggests statistical non-significance. In both panels, PBC and PTI stand for perceived behavioral control and public transport infrastructure respectively. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

especially for the effect of residing in detached house and for following emissions of an action. It is also noteworthy that personal norm becomes cross-sectorally influential for EV adoption and energy-saving measures, if one just considers the revealed preferences studies.

As the super categories integrate even more factors than previously with factor categories, we will also analyze in more detail some of the statistically significant underlying evidence from panel b. Doing this, and considering also the statistically significant data points underlying

panel b of Fig. 6, for most super categories the direction of influence shown by the majority of the statistically significant evidence is consistent across the different choices, i.e. they either support or discourage the choices. Exceptions to this are public transport infrastructure, respondent's age, access to car, trip distance, income, environmental attitude, education, and gender which influence the choices heterogeneously in terms of the direction of the effect.

The results suggest that the improvement of public transport

infrastructure can affect transport modes differently, in the sense that although it increases the likelihood of choosing public transport modes, it discourages active transport, and car use, when also the statistically significant pieces of evidence from panel b are considered. Hence, it turns into a dilemma for policymakers; while car use can be reduced by facilitating public transport, it may decrease active transport as well. Some studies conducted outside the Nordic countries, however, disagree with this finding [79]. For instance, a study showed that the frequency of walking can increase, if the bus stops are located within 400 m of the starting destination [80]. The statistically significant evidence also shows that, unsurprisingly, car access positively affects car use and discourages the use of public and active transport. Statistically significant evidence also shows that longer trip distances increase the likelihood of adopting less pro-environmental choices, affecting EV adoption, and use of public and active transport modes.

Income, as one of the critical socioeconomic characteristics, is surprisingly found to be either non-influential or inconclusive for all the choices for which there is evidence. Nevertheless, the statistically significant evidence for income indicates that it influences the choices positively except for the choice of active transport. This suggests that higher income levels increase the chances of adopting some pro-environmental behaviors that generally are perceived to require financial means that not everyone may have, such as the adoption of EVs and heat pumps, and implementing energy-saving, but also surprisingly the use of public transport. With that said, higher income does also increase the likelihood of using a car and discourages other environmentally friendly choices, such as biking and walking.

Regarding the other exceptions, and based on the statistically significant evidence, older respondents show more interest in buying EVs (however, age squared affects EV adoption negatively, see panel b in Fig. 6), using cars and active modes, and adopting heat pumps, while they seem to be less motivated to use public transport, purchase new electric or solid fuel heating systems. The results show that educated people are more willing to adopt EVs, but less likely to buy heat pumps and solid heaters or implement measures to save energy at home. The statistically significant evidence also indicates that men are more inclined to purchase EVs, use car and active modes for transport, whereas women have a higher likelihood of implementing energy-saving measures. Furthermore, the statistically significant evidence suggests that environmental attitude promotes the choice of EV and active transport, whereas it discourages the purchase of new heating system.

Our analysis further confirmed that geography can play an important role in decision-making, suggesting that living in a specific region (e.g. countries and cities) and area (e.g. rural, suburban, urban, and district heating areas) affects the likelihood of leaning toward sustainable behaviors in EV adoption, choice of heating system, and implementation of energy-saving measures (panel a in Fig. 6).

We identified the effect of past behaviors and choices in decision-making for transport mode and heating system adoption. The results propose that owning a specific heating technology makes the adoption of some technologies (both the existing one, representing repetition decision strategy, and in some cases, other technologies, see Table 2) more likely. Our findings also recognized the effect of habitual behaviors on the mode choice of car for transport (see Table 2). These findings reflect the inertia in adopting more sustainable pro-environmental behaviors, which is in line with the findings of others from outside the Nordics [81–83].

Furthermore, the results are generally in harmony with the well-established theories of decision-making, such as the theory of planned behavior [84] and value-belief-norm theory [85,86], since the influence of attitude, environmental attitude, perceived behavioral control, subjective norm, personal norm, and environmental norms has been confirmed by our analysis. However, the results demonstrate some deviations from the theories for some of the decisions, for instance, environmental concerns for EV adoption, attitude for car use, subjective norm for public transport use, personal norm and environmental

attitude for active transport, and perceived behavioral control, subjective norm, environmental concerns for energy-saving measures are found to be non-influential.

The key intended novelty of our work is the analysis of common factors affecting key energy-related decisions. To do so, we have developed a meta-analysis method aimed at addressing the particularities of this work. In comparison to the other common meta-analyses, our method is less focused on the effect sizes of the factors. This is driven by both, our aim to assess, at least in aggregate, all the factors affecting decisions found in the literature, and by the lack of evidence for some factors, preventing a proper statistical analysis. A methodology with similarities to ours can be found in ref. [6]. Here the authors also analyzed evidence, based on the statistical significance and the direction of influence, and focused on the acceptance of EVs. Like us, the authors also found contradicting results from the body of literature.

The previous literature reviews and meta-analyses on the energy-related decisions we focus on have unanimously indicated that there is a need for more investigation of pro-environmental behaviors in energy-related decisions [6–16]. The present analysis of common factors influencing the decisions, in turn, emphasizes the research on the characteristics of the consumers that can lead toward such climate-friendly behaviors. Our study thus is an effort to consolidate various streams of disciplinary research and could further be used for identifying and targeting different segments of consumers for policy interventions.

4. Conclusions

We conducted an interdisciplinary systematic literature review and meta-analysis to improve our understanding of the determinant factors of four energy-related decisions. We identified the factors influencing the decisions consistently in terms of direction of effect and statistical significance. A group of factors, namely attitude, comfort, costs, living in a detached house, emission implications of the choice, perceived behavioral control, environmental friendliness of the technology, and subjective norm, affect multiple choices uniformly in terms of the direction of effect and statistical significance. However, the analysis revealed that some factors affecting multiple decisions support or discourage environmentally benign choices depending on the context (e.g. better public transport infrastructure encourages public transport use but discourages active modes). Nevertheless, for most of the factors the direction of influence suggested by the majority of the statistically significant evidence is consistent across the different choices, suggesting that a given underlying factor tends to either support or discourage all the choices (or not be influential at all for some of them). We also showed that how consistent the evidence base is across the studies for each factor in terms of statistical significance and direction of the influence.

Our analysis sheds light on the differences between results based on revealed and stated preferences surveys, differentiating the influential factors based on this criterion. We highlight the extent to which our conclusions regarding the factors change, if only revealed preferences evidence is considered. It is shown that for EV adoption the statistical significance of factors generally increases, when stated preference surveys are excluded. We also identified factor categories for which combining stated and revealed preference surveys was the source of inconclusiveness, and using just the empirical evidence allowed one to draw conclusions that could not be drawn from the combined data.

We found out that although the evidence base is strong in terms of having a considerable amount of empirical evidence (65 out of 114 pieces of evidence were based also on revealed preferences, rather than just on stated preferences), the multiplicity of evidence for many factors is low having only one piece of evidence. As for the factors that we were able to conduct the analysis for, several of them were supported by only two pieces of evidence which weakens any conclusions that can be drawn about their influence. On top of that, many identified influential factors suffer from not being supported by any revealed preferences

study. Accordingly, we argue that further empirical investigation on the determinant factor of energy-related decisions is needed.

In this review and meta-analysis, we aimed to assess all the factors that have been identified in the literature to influence the four important energy-related decisions. As a next step, we feel it could be useful to dive into some of the *Inconclusive* factor categories and try to better understand the causes for the differences that were observed across the findings of different studies. We further suggest extending the scope of the review to other geographical areas to examine the possible effect of cultural and contextual variations on these decisions. Furthermore, since various issues could affect the results of meta-analysis such as the *Table 2* fallacy [77] and publication bias [78], we suggest that future works focus on identifying these issues and possible ways to deal with them.

Finally, the findings of this research can support the policymakers to design more effective, comprehensive, and informed behavioral interventions for the residential and transport sectors to induce the required changes and achieve the energy transition targets [8]. Such efforts could for instance target certain sociodemographic groups identified through the results of this analysis to promote pro-environmental energy-related decisions. Also, as some psychological factors turned out to be important, specific behavioral interventions can be crafted to shape positive attitudes toward environmentally friendly behaviors.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Behzad Zamanipour: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Ilkka Keppo:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2024.103861>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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